

Fast Converging Robust Adaptive Arrays

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Abstract—A pseudo-median canceller is introduced as the canonical processor of a robust adaptive array method which significantly reduces the deleterious effects of non-Gaussian, real-world noise and interference (outliers) on typical array performance metrics such as (normalized) output noise power residue and signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR). In addition, the proposed structure offers natural protection against signal cancellation, or equivalently, against an increase in the output noise power residue, when weight-training data contains desired signal components. The convergence rate is shown to be commensurate with Sample Matrix Inversion (SMI) methods for Gaussian noise and interference, and convergence is essentially unaffected when outliers are added to the Gaussian weight-training data, while non-robust SMI methods slow significantly under the same circumstances.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the lack of *a priori* knowledge of an external environment, adaptive techniques require a certain amount of data to effectively estimate the input noise and interference (from here on simply termed 'noise') covariance matrix. The amount of data (the number of statistically independent samples) required so that the SINR performance of the adaptive processor is close (nominally within 3dB) to the optimum is called the convergence measure of effectiveness (MOE) of the processor. Minimizing the convergence MOE is important since in many environments the external interference is non-stationary. For the pure statistically stationary Gaussian noise case, it has been shown that the convergence MOE of the standard adaptive linear technique, the SMI algorithm [1], can be attained using approximately $2N$ samples for weight estimation, regardless of the external noise covariance matrix, where N is the number of degrees of freedom in the processor. (N is equal to the number of antenna channels (i.e., antenna elements or subarrays) for a spatially adaptive array processor, and equal to the number of space-time channels in a Space-Time Adaptive Processing (STAP) processor). Referred to as the SMI convergence MOE, it has become the benchmark used to assess convergence rates of adaptive processors. Faster methods using eigenanalysis techniques exist [6], but this paper deals with comparing the new proposed method with the SMI method. Robustification of the eigenanalysis techniques is a topic of future research. The proposed robust adaptive array algorithm has a convergence MOE commensurate with the SMI method for Gaussian noise environments *with or without* outlier data values present. Fast convergence rates are important for several practical reasons including limited

amounts of weight training data due to non-stationary/non-homogeneous noise and adaptive weight computational complexity.

Real data often contain non-Gaussian/outlier values (impulsive noise). The performance degradation of the SMI algorithm in the presence of non-Gaussian/outlier contaminant data values can be attributed to the highly sensitive nature of covariance matrix estimates to even small amounts of impulsive noise (for example, possibly due to clutter discretized in radar [2]) that may be corrupting the dominant noise distribution. For contaminated data, it will be illustrated how convergence rate slows significantly. In this paper, a method that accommodates non-Gaussian/outlier contaminated data and still produces an SMI-like convergence rate is presented. Also, it is seen that desired signal cancellation, or equivalently, an increase in the output noise power residue [10], is significantly reduced by this method when training data has desired signal components. Although the treatment here is concerned with a spatially adaptive array, the results may be extended directly to STAP applications as well, for instance in airborne radar systems. In section II, we show how a general adaptive array may be transformed to (and implemented as) a Gram-Schmidt cascaded canceller configuration. Section III introduces the pseudo-median canceller structure as a robust surrogate for the Gram-Schmidt cascaded canceller, and theoretical convergence results are presented and compared to SMI processors for Gaussian statistics. Simulation results are presented with discussion in Section IV showing robust, SMI-like convergence.

II. EQUIVALENT TRANSFORMATIONS

A. General Adaptive Array: Sidelobe Canceller Form

A general, linear adaptive array (Fig. 1) with a single mainbeam steering vector constraint (called a Minimum-

Fig. 1 General linear adaptive array processor: q is the input vector, y is the output vector, w is the complex weight vector. H denotes Hermitian or conjugate-transpose operation.

Variance Distortionless Response (MVDR) beamformer [3]) can be converted to its equivalent sidelobe canceller form via a unitary, non-singular, square matrix transformation of the input data vector \mathbf{q} [4],[5]. It can be shown that *any* non-singular, matrix transformation of the inputs of a general adaptive array does not change the adaptive SINR if weight adaptation using SMI is subsequently carried out using an identically transformed steering vector [5]. Thus, a linear transformation can be chosen that moves all desired signal energy into a single "main" channel (as well as some noise), leaving only (transformed) noise in the remaining "auxiliary" channels, creating a sidelobe canceller form, \mathbf{u} , of the input data vector, \mathbf{q} . The first element or "main channel" of \mathbf{u} is labeled $u_m = u_1$ and "auxiliary channels" are labeled $\mathbf{u}_a = \mathbf{u}_n$, $n=2, \dots, N$.

A sidelobe canceller [7],[8] is a specific form of a general adaptive array where the $N \times 1$ desired signal (steering) vector is set to $[1 \ 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T$, the "main" or first channel weight is fixed to unity, and the $(N-1) \times 1$ auxiliary channel adaptive weight vector estimate $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_a$ ($\hat{\cdot}$ denotes 'estimate of') solves the adaptive Wiener-Hopf matrix equation,

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_a = \hat{\mathbf{R}}_a^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{am}, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_a$ is the $(N-1) \times (N-1)$ auxiliary channel covariance matrix estimate, and $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{am}$ is the $(N-1) \times 1$ cross-correlation vector estimate between the main channel and the auxiliary channels. For Gaussian statistics, the maximum likelihood estimates of these quantities are

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_a = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{u}_a(k) \mathbf{u}_a(k)^H \quad (2)$$

and

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{am} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{u}_a(k) u_m(k)^* \quad (3)$$

where K is the number of samples (snapshots) used in the averages and $*$ denotes complex conjugate operation. When employing (2) and (3), the sidelobe canceller uses the SMI algorithm, and its scalar output, g , is (using vector partitioning)

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{w}_{slc}^H \mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \dots \\ -\hat{\mathbf{w}}_a \end{bmatrix}^H \mathbf{u}. \quad (4)$$

B. Sidelobe Canceller: Gram-Schmidt Cascaded Canceller Form

It is known that the SMI-based sidelobe canceller in (4) has an equivalent Gram-Schmidt cascaded canceller form in

the steady state [8] and in the transient state with numerically identical outputs [4], where transient state refers to the case where weights are estimated from finite length data vectors. Infinite (perfect) numerical accuracy is assumed, i.e., the cascaded weights correspond to a numerically equivalent set of linear weights (1) that can be applied directly to the transformed array input data vector \mathbf{u} via (4), if so desired.

A Gram-Schmidt canceller [8] is shown in Fig. 2a for the $N = 4$ channel case. It is comprised of six identical (Fig. 2b) two-input canceller building blocks. The symbol L_2 in each block means the optimal weight estimate for that block is calculated by minimizing the square of the L_2 -norm of the residual output vector from that block, over some specified number of K weight-training samples.

Fig. 2 (a) Equivalent Gram-Schmidt cascaded processor for $N=4$ case. (b) Any single building block canceller.

In the following, for notational simplicity, the left input of *any single* building block (Fig. 2b) is relabeled z , the right input is relabeled x , and the output is relabeled r . Each block serves to have the component of z , which is correlated with x , subtracted from z . This is accomplished by choosing an optimum weight estimate \hat{w}_{opt} such that the residual r is statistically orthogonal to x . The *least-squares* method is used to minimize, over the set of complex weights w , the square of the L_2 norm of the residual output $r = z - w^* x$ where $r = r(k)$, $z = z(k)$, and $x = x(k)$, for $k = 1, \dots, K$; i.e., for any single building block,

$$\hat{w}_{opt} = \arg \min_w \left[\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K |z(k) - w^* x(k)|^2 \right]. \quad (5)$$

This results in the *scalar* adaptive Wiener-Hopf equation,

$$\hat{w}_{opt} = \hat{R}_{xx}^{-1} \hat{r}_{zx} \quad (6)$$

where maximum likelihood estimates again may be used for the scalar covariance estimates, assuming Gaussian statistics, as

$$\hat{R}_{xx} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K x(k)x(k)^* \quad (7)$$

and

$$\hat{r}_{zx} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K x(k)z(k)^* \quad (8)$$

Note that (7) and (8) are sensitive to non-Gaussian/outlier contaminants just like their matrix counterparts in (2) and (3).

III. PSEUDO-MEDIAN CANCELLER

It was discussed in section II how the general adaptive array processor may be equivalently transformed (in terms of SINR) into its Gram-Schmidt cascaded canceller form, and the adaptive implementation was shown to be a cascaded set of operationally identical, two-input canceller building blocks. With this in mind, algorithm modifications are made to these L_2 blocks in order to improve robustness to non-Gaussian noise/outliers that may be present in the data used for weight training. A new algorithm, using a *robust* two-input canceller building block, will be shown to produce the same optimal weight as the Gram-Schmidt L_2 block. For this robust, two-input building block, the non-linear *sample median* function is used, and the new block is subsequently labeled L_{med} .

A. The L_{med} building block

Set $w_k = (z(k)/x(k))^*$, $k=1, 2, \dots, K$, and assume K is odd. Take the *sample median* of the real parts of $\{w_k\}$ as the real part of the new optimal weight, and next take the sample median of the imaginary parts of $\{w_k\}$ as the imaginary part of the new optimal weight. It will be shown that, with no outliers and as $K \rightarrow \infty$, the resulting weight,

$$w_{med} = \underset{k=1 \text{ to } K}{MED} \left[\text{real} \left(\frac{z(k)}{x(k)} \right)^* \right] + j \left\{ \underset{k=1 \text{ to } K}{MED} \left[\text{imag} \left(\frac{z(k)}{x(k)} \right)^* \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

converges to the same optimal complex weight as an L_2 block using the same input data. This assumes that both z and x each have a zero mean, Gaussian probability density function (*pdf*) (or cumulative distribution function (*cdf*)) for both their real and imaginary parts, or even more broadly, *only* assuming that all four *pdf*'s are symmetric (i.e., z and x each have *complex symmetric densities*). In (9), K is assumed odd,

MED refers to the *sample median*, $j = \sqrt{-1}$ is the unit imaginary number, *real* means "real part of", and *imag* means "imaginary part of".

We drop the explicit k dependence from the random variables z , x , r , and w , for notational simplicity, and assume $K \rightarrow \infty$ in the following development. Starting with the L_2 building block canceller, if *a priori* knowledge of the scalar auxiliary channel covariance R_{xx} and scalar cross-correlation r_{zx} were available, the optimal weight is obtained using *mean square error* (MSE) criterion and results in the two-input, scalar, Wiener-Hopf equation, $w_{opt} = R_{xx}^{-1} r_{zx}$. Define $r_u = z - w_{opt}^* x$ as the residual value output after optimal weighting is applied. r_u is uncorrelated with x by definition. Solving for z yields $z = r_u + w_{opt}^* x$, and substituting this into $w = (z/x)^*$ from (9), results in

$$w = \left(\frac{z}{x} \right)^* = \frac{r_u^* + w_{opt}^* x^*}{x^*} = \left(\frac{r_u}{x} \right)^* + w_{opt} \quad (10)$$

Taking, separately, the *statistical medians* of the real and imaginary parts of (10) yields

$$w_{med,r,i} = \text{med}_{r,i} \left[\left(\frac{r_u}{x} \right)^* + w_{opt} \right] = \text{med}_{r,i} \left[\left(\frac{r_u}{x} \right)^* \right] + w_{opt,r,i} \quad (11)$$

where $\text{med}_{r,i}$ refers to the statistical median of both of the real and imaginary parts separately, and similarly for $w_{opt,r,i}$; since $w_{opt,r,i}$ are constants, they come out of the median function.

Next, we show that $\text{med}_{r,i}[(r_u/x)^*] = 0$, for the case where z and x are each zero mean, complex Gaussian random variables (also true for any complex symmetric densities), yielding the desired components of the optimal weight, $w_{opt} = w_{opt,r} + jw_{opt,i}$.

The random quantity r_u is a linear combination of z and x and is therefore a zero mean, complex Gaussian random variable. Since r_u and x are uncorrelated and Gaussian, they are independent. We normalize the quotient $(r_u/x)^*$ by multiplying by the ratio of standard deviations,

$$s = \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_{r_u}} \left(\frac{r_u}{x} \right)^* = \left(\frac{r_u^\circ}{x^\circ} \right)^* \quad (12)$$

where σ_x and σ_{r_u} are the standard deviations of x and r_u , respectively, and x° and r_u° are normalized versions of x and r_u , respectively, each with unit variance. The *pdf* and *cdf* of $s_{r,i}$ (subscripts r and i refer to the real and imaginary parts of

s , separately) were derived, and results are given here, respectively, as

$$f_{s_{r,i}}(s_{r,i}) = \frac{1}{2(s_{r,i}^2 + 1)^{3/2}}, \quad -\infty \leq s_{r,i} \leq \infty, \quad (13)$$

and

$$F_{s_{r,i}}(s_{r,i}) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{s_{r,i}}{2(s_{r,i}^2 + 1)^{1/2}}, \quad -\infty \leq s_{r,i} \leq \infty, \quad (14)$$

where it is readily seen in Fig. 3 and via (13) that $med_{r,i}(s) = 0$. Using the fact that $med_{r,i}(ay) = a med_{r,i}(y)$ for any real constant a and any complex random variable y , (11) becomes (via (12)),

$$w_{med_{r,i}} = w_{opt_{r,i}}. \quad (15)$$

Therefore $w_{med} \rightarrow w_{opt}$ as $K \rightarrow \infty$, as claimed for (9). The convergence performance of w_{med} will be derived next, for Gaussian statistics.

Fig. 3. pdf of real or imaginary parts of $s = (r^o/x^o)^*$. $f_{s_{r,i}}(s_{r,i})$ and $s_{r,i}$ refer separately to the real, r , and imaginary, i , parts of $f_s(s)$ and s .

B. Convergence of L_{med} block: no outliers

For adaptive implementations of the two-input pseudo-median canceller (i.e., for finite K), the order statistics pdf of $s_{r,i}$ [9],

$$f_p(s_{r,i}) = \frac{K!}{(p-1)!(K-p)!} F_{s_{r,i}}^{p-1}(s_{r,i}) \times [1 - F_{s_{r,i}}(s_{r,i})]^{K-p} f_{s_{r,i}}(s_{r,i}), \quad (16)$$

is used to determine the median order statistics of $s_{r,i}$, using (13) and (14), where $p = (K+1)/2$ is the median (for K odd).

Due to space limitations, just the results will be presented: using (12), the means of the median order statistics were found to be zero, and the variances of the median order statistics were found to be: $\text{var}(med_{r,i}(s)) = 1/(K-1)$ (where 'var' denotes variance), for K an odd integer and $K > 1$. Thus, because $\text{var}(ay) = a^2 \text{var}(y)$ holds for any real constant a and for any real random variable y , the variance of $w_{med_{r,i}}$ (11) is

$$\text{var}(w_{med_{r,i}}) = \frac{\sigma_{r_u}^2}{\sigma_x^2} \left(\frac{1}{K-1} \right). \quad (17)$$

This variance will be used in the following derivation of the analytical convergence rate.

The figure of merit often used to assess canceller performance is the normalized output residue power (NORP), here labeled η , and it is approximately equal to the inverse of the SINR performance metric for non-concurrent processing [4]. (Non-concurrent processing refers to the case where weights are trained using *secondary* training data, but are applied to statistically independent *primary* data possibly containing desired signal components.) This provides justification for directly comparing the SINR convergence MOE to the NORP convergence MOE since desired signal, which is only in the primary data (in the main channel), is assumed to pass through the canceller unaffected. For a two-input canceller, η is defined as,

$$\eta = \frac{E\{|z - w_o^* x|^2\}}{res_{opt}}, \quad (18)$$

where w_o is the weight chosen under some arbitrary performance criterion, E denotes expectation, and

$$res_{opt} = E\{|z - w_{opt}^* x|^2\} \quad (19)$$

is the optimal (minimum) residue power found by using $w_{opt} = R_{xx}^{-1} r_{xz}$. If w_o in (18) is chosen under MSE criterion, then $w_o = w_{opt}$, and η achieves its minimum value of 1, or equivalently, 0 dB. However, this requires perfect *a priori* knowledge of the relevant statistics, so for adaptive methods such as SMI or L_{med} criterion,

$$w_o = w_{opt} + \tilde{w}, \quad (20)$$

where \tilde{w} is some difference weight from the complex constant w_{opt} . Since $r_u = z - w_{opt}^* x$, using (18) and (20) we have

$$\eta = \frac{E\{|z - w_{opt}^* x - \tilde{w}^* x|^2\}}{res_{opt}} = \frac{E\{|r_u - \tilde{w}^* x|^2\}}{res_{opt}}, \quad (21)$$

and,

$$res_{opt} = E\{|z - w_{opt}^* x|^2\} = E\{|r_u|^2\} = \sigma_{r_u}^2. \quad (22)$$

Since r_u is uncorrelated with x by definition, we know that $E\{r_u x^* \} = E\{x r_u^* \} = 0$, so, from the numerator of (21),

$$E\{|r_u - \tilde{w}^* x|^2\} = \sigma_{r_u}^2 + |\tilde{w}|^2 \sigma_x^2, \quad (23)$$

thus, substituting (22) and (23) into (21), results in

$$\eta = 1 + |\tilde{w}|^2 \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_{r_u}^2} = 1 + \tilde{w}_r^2 \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_{r_u}^2} + \tilde{w}_i^2 \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_{r_u}^2}. \quad (24)$$

Note that subscripts r and i refer to the real and imaginary components of \tilde{w} , respectively.

The quantity w_{med} in (9) was shown to converge to w_{opt} , and its variance about the mean of w_{opt} , as a function of K , was given in (17) for both the real and imaginary parts of the weights. For the two-input pseudo-median canceller, $\tilde{w}_{r,i} = w_{med,r,i} - w_{opt,r,i}$, so $E\{\tilde{w}_r^2\} = E\{\tilde{w}_i^2\} = \text{var}(w_{med,r,i}) = \sigma_{r_u}^2 / [\sigma_x^2 (1/(K-1))]$. Thus, from (24), the average convergence rate for the L_{med} block is found to be

$$E\{\eta\} = 1 + 2/(K-1), \quad (25)$$

for zero mean, complex Gaussian inputs (z and x). In comparison, the standard L_2 block converges just slightly faster: $1+1/(K-1)$, for the same assumptions [4], but, as will be shown in the next section, it is not nearly as robust as the L_{med} block. Lastly, it is noted that the *two-input* L_{med} algorithm just derived, has, like the two input SMI (L_2) algorithm, a convergence rate shown here to be only a function of the number of samples, K , and thus is *independent* of the two-input, external covariance matrix.

C. N-Input Pseudo-Median Canceller

Replacing the L_2 blocks with L_{med} blocks throughout a cascaded canceller results in the cascaded canceller configuration shown in Fig. 4.

IV. CONVERGENCE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We compared the performance of the SMI and Pseudo-Median Canceller (PMC) in the presence of a single sample outlier in the training data. The outlier was given a range of

Fig. 4. (a) Pseudo-median canceller using L_{med} building blocks for $N=4$ case. (b) Any single L_{med} building block canceller.

powers, normalized to the internal noise level. The outlier was restricted to be in the training data only. Adapted weights were *not* applied to data used to train the adapted weights. Instead, they were applied to statistically independent data (non-concurrent processing was used). For a canceller configuration, the desired signal in the main channel is passed through to the output with unity gain while only correlated noise (interference) is removed at each stage.

For simulation graphs shown next, outliers were only added to the main channel (u_1) in the training data, emulating the addition of a scaled desired-signal vector, $[\alpha \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T$, where α^2 is the outlier or added signal power. (The addition of outliers to all channels or to just the auxiliary channels only, resulted in much less degradation of the SMI convergence rate for all outlier power levels (results not shown here.)) It will be seen for the PMC that desired signal components present in the main channel of the training data have a significantly reduced effect on noise cancellation.

Convergence plots for the SMI (L_2) cascaded canceller are shown in Fig. 5, for various outlier powers. η_{avg} , a Monte Carlo average of 20 normalized output residue powers, is plotted vs. K , the number of training samples used. $N = 10$ channels were chosen, and one +20dB narrowband Gaussian noise barrage sidelobe jammer (20dB above internal receiver noise power) plus uncorrelated Gaussian noise were modeled as inputs in the simulations shown here. The SMI algorithm predicts 3dB convergence in about $K = 2N = 20$ samples, which appears to be satisfied for plots corresponding to negligible power outlier values (-10dB to +10dB). However, as the outlier power increases, it is evident that convergence slows significantly. For example, for a single +20dB outlier, the convergence MOE is about 27 samples; for a single +30dB outlier, many more than 50 samples are required. For

Fig. 5 Convergence plots of SMI (L_2) cascaded canceller, $N=10$ case. Number of jammers = 1. Outliers degrade performance significantly.

Fig. 6 Convergence plots of pseudo-median (L_{med}) cascaded canceller, $N=10$ case. Number of jammers = 1. Outliers have little effect on performance.

three +20dB outliers (equal to the jammer level and therefore difficult to prescreen) (graph not shown here) the convergence MOE is 48 samples.

For the PMC, also with $N=10$, Fig. 6 shows that convergence is essentially unaffected by the addition of outliers of any power level, and that it is approximately equal to the ideal SMI convergence rate in pure Gaussian jammer and noise environments. In fact, for 3 and even 5 outliers of any power level (graphs not shown here), convergence is still essentially unaffected. Thus, it is evident that strong desired signals in the training data cause little loss in noise cancellation; the PMC equivalent weight vector quickly approaches the optimum weight vector and the median function essentially ignores the added desired signal vector.

It is well-known for the SMI algorithm with no outliers, that the convergence rate is independent of the input noise covariance matrix for both the two input and general N -input (Fig. 2) cases [1],[4]. Yet, for the pseudo-median canceller (Fig. 4), for the same assumptions, it appears from simulation (graphs not shown here) that this strict invariance to the input covariance matrix is limited to just the two input case. However, simulations not shown here indicate that this invariance property, for N inputs, *does* hold for cases where the number of discrete interference sources is approximately one-third or less of the total number of degrees of freedom N , representing many realistic (low rank) interference scenarios. For more interference sources above this threshold, the convergence rate degrades gracefully and eventually becomes similar to the SMI/Gram-Schmidt canceller with outliers present in the training data.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A new, robust, cascaded canceller was introduced which significantly reduces the effect outliers have on convergence rate. For Gaussian statistics, an analytical convergence rate was derived for the two-input case. For general N inputs, simulations showed standard SMI cancellers had poor convergence in the presence of outliers, but the N input pseudo-median canceller was essentially unaffected. In addition, it appears desired signals in weight training data cause little loss in noise cancellation. Further work is planned to fully characterize this new adaptive architecture.

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